

THE STUDY OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN LINGUOCULTUROLOGY

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Abstract. The present article elucidates the issues of studying phraseological units in linguoculturology. The theoretical analyses of researching phraseologisms in terms of culture, the view of the world linguists and their studies have been observed. Finding the analogues and equivalents for phraseological units in different languages requires linguocultural approach.

Key words: linguoculturology, phraseology, culture, equivalent, analogues, lacuna.

The issue of studying phraseological units in modern linguistics is extremely relevant and significant, attracting the attention of many researchers. The study of phraseological units is directly related to the culture of the nation, folk customs, traditions, worldview, history, social life and lifestyle. Therefore, the study of phraseological units reveals the specific features of the nation and these national features are expressed through language. Nation and language are closely related to each other. Therefore, the combination of two areas, such as linguistics and cultural studies, ensures the formation of concepts such as culture, language and national mentality as a single integrated system, while understanding and studying the mechanisms of this system through scientific approaches creates a basis for the preservation of national cultural values by embedding them in the language.

Therefore, V.A.Maslova recognizes linguocultural studies as a science that arose in the conflict between linguistics and cultural studies. The object of study of this science is the culture of the people reflected in the language.

When we study a language, we involuntarily approach the nation that speaks this language, the diversity of the language, the expressiveness of language units are associated with the consciousness of the nation. The object of study of the linguocultural direction of linguistics includes various language units and linguistic means. Phraseological units are also an object of study of the science of linguocultural studies, since phraseological units are a product of folk creativity and reflect the definition and description of the nation.

The interrelationship of language and culture has been studied for two centuries. However, the science of linguocultural studies emerged in the 20th century and was recognized as a separate independent field, and the number of studies conducted in this area is increasing, and the topics studied are expanding.

Language is a carrier of culture and reflects the experience of the nation accumulated over the centuries. As a result, within each language, a special national system is formed for its speakers, and a national picture of the world is formed. The phenomena of existence, the world around us, the actions taking place in the environment, various situations in life are reflected through the lexical system of the language. At the same time, for each language community, these differences and a special “content mapping” process takes place. That is, in thinking and consciousness of the language owners, language units that are distinguished by their national and cultural characteristics are embodied. When approached linguistically, these language units are interpreted as “linguoculturalism”. In most cases, these language units constitute everyday objects and clothing, and it is necessary to include not only lexical units, but also phraseological units.

The field of linguistic and cultural studies was formed on the basis of the theories of A.A.Potebnya, Sh.Balli, G.Shpet, L.Weisgerber, R. Barth, V.V.Vinogradov, A.Vezhbitskaya, Yu.D.Apresyan about the interrelation of culture and language, their observations are still relevant today.

Foreign scientists have paid attention to the study of phraseology in the field of linguistic and cultural studies. In particular, E.I. Haugen and E. Sapir, studying the phraseological system of the language from the perspective of linguistic and cultural studies, reflected on the culture of peoples reflected in the language and emphasized the direct connection of phraseologisms with the “linguistic world picture”. W. von Humboldt, drawing attention to the national content of the language, expressed the opinion that “the more the language is interconnected with the national spirit and the more the national spirit influences the language, the higher the development of the language can reach”. Russian linguists V.N.Teliya, L.I.Rozeynson, N.F.Alefirenko paid attention to the study of phraseological units through a linguocultural approach. These scientists discussed in detail the incorporation of culture and the linguistic world picture into the content of phraseologisms through a linguocultural approach. Linguocultural study of phraseological units is also widely carried out in Uzbek linguistics. In particular, modern researchers such as L.G.Yusupova and N.B.Azizova have contributed to the study of phraseologisms. L.G.Yusupova emphasized that in conducting in-depth analyses of phraseological units, opportunities arise to reveal the spiritual and material culture of the people.

The field of linguocultural studies also covers issues of various areas of linguistics. In particular, in the field of linguocultural studies, phraseologisms can

be studied from various perspectives. Therefore, linguocultural studies, being connected with other areas, requires a coordinated approach to the issues of semiotics, cognitive linguistics, semantics, and ethnolinguistics. Therefore, within the framework of this study, special attention is paid to the components of phraseologisms. We should note the contribution of scientists who have conducted research in this area due to the analysis we have conducted. In particular, phraseologisms were studied from an ethnolinguistic point of view by Ye.A.Berezovich, S.M. and N.I.Tolstiye, and from a lexical semantic point of view by Yu.D.Apresyan and A.Vezhbitskaya, whose theoretical approaches have been reflected in a number of scientific studies to date.

According to N.S.Trubetsky, “the linguocultural approach to phraseology is based on the embodiment of cultural values in the language and their preservation in the language.”

Phraseologisms reflect the rich experience of the people associated with their everyday work, lifestyle, customs, and culture. A.I.Yefimov approaches the interpretation of phraseological units figuratively, comparing them with precious stones and gold that adorn the language. Phraseologisms cover all aspects of human life, that is, the industriousness or laziness of a person, human intelligence and ignorance, negative and positive aspects of human character, wealth and poverty, human activity, place in society, attitude to others, revealing the unique characteristics of each nation. Phraseologisms are considered a means of speech and can convey human thought through figurative symbols. It is not difficult to understand phraseologisms within the framework of one language, because from an early age a person understands that language is formed through images, and the figurative expression of language is absorbed into the human mind. Although it is not difficult to understand phraseologisms within the framework of one language, understanding phraseologisms in another language, their correct interpretation and appropriate use are extremely urgent issues. Therefore, in the comparative study of phraseologisms, studying their linguistic and cultural issues and proposing appropriate equivalents and analogues in another language is of practical importance today. When searching for analogues of phraseologisms, not only the lexical and syntactic system of each language is taken into account, but also the linguocultural aspect. In most cases, the emergence of phraseologisms is caused by historical events, the specific culture of the people, which cannot be reflected in the language of another people, and therefore a lacuna occurs. That is, if there is no suitable equivalent of phraseologisms, their analogues and variants are searched for or expressed through interpretation.

Summing up, it should be said that linguocultural studies of phraseologisms promote deeper understanding the national values of each folk, help compare the way of appearance of phraseologisms in the language.

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